

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of some New Bis(2-pyrazolino-3-yl)benzenes

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Several new 3,3'-*m*-phenylenebis(5-aryl-2-pyrazolines) (4) have been prepared by the reaction of 1,1'-(1,3-phenylene)bis(3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (3) with hydrazine hydrate in alcohol. Their *N*-substituted derivatives 4a-d have been prepared by nitrosation, acetylation, benzylation and benzenesulphonylation of 4. Further, 5,5'-*p*-phenylenebis(3-aryl-2-pyrazolines) (8) have also been prepared by the reaction of 3,3'-(1,4-phenylene)bis(1-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (7) with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid. Structures of the compounds have been confirmed by ir and pmr spectral data. They have been screened against a few microorganisms for antibacterial and antifungal activities.

THE chemistry of pyrazolines have attracted much attention because of their wide spectrum of physiological activity¹. Hence, a systematic study on the synthesis and possible physiological activity has been considered. Amongst the various methods for the synthesis of pyrazolines, the reactions involving diazo compounds and hydrazines have gained importance because of their elegance. We reported earlier the synthesis of 3-arylsulphonyl-2-pyrazolines², 3-aryl-4-aryl-2-pyrazolines³ and bis-(4-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)ketones⁴ by the cycloaddition of diazocompounds to sulphonyl and carbonyl activated double bonds. Several workers reported the synthesis of 2-pyrazolines by the reaction of alkyl and arylhydrazines with α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds under a variety of experimental conditions⁵⁻¹⁰. Recently the synthesis of 5,5'-*p*-phenylenebis(3-aryl-2-pyrazolines)^{11,12}, 3,3'-*p*-phenylenebis(5-aryl-2-pyrazolines)¹³ and 2,4-bis-(4,5-dihydro-5-arylpyrazol-3-yl)phenols¹⁴ have been reported by the reaction of hydrazines with different Michael acceptors. However, the synthesis of 3,3'-*m*-phenylenebis(5-aryl-2-pyrazolines) (4) has not yet been reported to the best of our knowledge. Hence, we report herein their synthesis by the reaction of 1,1'-(1,3-phenylene)bis(3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (3) with hydrazine hydrate in alcohol at reflux temperatures (Scheme 1, Table 1).

Further, in order to confirm the structures of 3,3'-*m*-phenylenebis(5-aryl-2-pyrazolines) (4) their 1-nitroso (4a), 1-acetyl (4b), 1-benzyloxy (4c) and 1-benzene-sulphonyl (4d) derivatives have been prepared by nitrosation, acetylation, benzylation and benzenesulphonylation of 4 (Scheme 2, Table 1). The formation of these compounds conclusively confirms the structures of bis(2-pyrazolines) (4).

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
4	H	165-66	82.24	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄
	4-OH ₂	175-76	80.45	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄
	4-(OH ₂) ₂ OH	179-80	81.35	C ₃₀ H ₃₄ N ₄
	4-OH ₂ O	186-87	79.56	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₂
	4-O ₂ H ₂ O	180-81	83.74	C ₂₈ H ₃₀ N ₄ O ₂
	4-F	164-66	70.50	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ F ₂
	4-Cl	178-77	79.77	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ Cl ₂
	4-Br	178-79	79.25	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ Br ₂
	4-NO ₂	189-40	81.66	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₂
	2,4-(OH ₂) ₂	173-74	75.48	C ₂₈ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₂

(Table 1 contd.)

4a	H	145-46	64.50	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂
	4-(CH ₃) ₂ OH	166-68	67.93	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂
	4-Cl	179-80	68.41	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₄ OCl ₂
4b	H	173-74	79.34	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂
	4-Cl	137-38	78.93	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ OCl ₂
	4-NO ₂	206-07	76.08	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂
4c	H	127-28	68.50	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂
	4-OH ₂	86-87	80.26	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂
	4-(CH ₃) ₂ OH	122-24	80.66	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂
4d	H	121-22	82.75	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
	4-CH ₃	127-28	74.50	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
	4-C ₂ H ₅ O	185-37	66.78	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
8	H	279-81	77.7	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂
	4-OH ₂	259-60	78.0	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂
	4-CH ₃ O	269-70	78.6	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄
	4-C ₂ H ₅ O	251-53	69.0	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₄
	4-Cl	263-64	67.3	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ OCl ₂
	4-Br	250-51	62.0	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ Br ₂ O ₂
	4-NH ₂	273-74	87.5	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂
	2,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂	265-56	83.2	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Scheme 2. Reagents: (i) NaNO₂/HCl, (ii) OH₂COOH, (iii) C₆H₅COCl/C₆H₅N, (iv) C₆H₅SO₂Cl/C₆H₅N.

Further, we also report the synthesis of 5,5'-(1,4-phenylene) bis(1-acetyl-4,5-dihydro-3-aryl-1H-pyrazoles) (8) by the reaction of 3,3'-(1,4-phenylene)bis(1-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (7) with hydrazine hydrate in presence of acetic acid (Scheme 3, Table 1). The compounds (8) were obtained in high yields directly from 7 in one step contrary to El-Rayyes Nizar *et al.*¹² who obtained the same in two steps.

The structures of 4, 4a-d and 8 were established by ir and nmr spectral data. These compounds exhibited ir bands at 3 280-3 220 (NH), 1 590-1 575 (C=N), 1 640-1 620 (C=O), 1 510-1 505 (N=O), 1 300-1 290 and 1 150-1 140 cm⁻¹ (SO₂). However, 4a-d and 8 did not show bands at 3 280-3 220 cm⁻¹ confirming the absence of NH group in these compounds. The ¹H nmr spectra

- 1; R=H
 2; R=4-OH₂
 3; R=4-OH₂O
 4; R=4-C₂H₅O
 5; R=4-Cl
 6; R=4-Br
 7; R=4-NH₂
 8; R=2,4-(OH₂O)₂

Scheme 3

of 4, 4a-d and 8 displayed an ABX pattern for the pyrazoline ring protons^{2-4,15-17}. Thus, the methylene protons appeared as doublet of doublets at δ 2.85-4.00 whereas the methine protons as triplets around δ 4.60-5.75. All the aromatic protons appeared as multiplets at 7.00-8.20. The spectra of 4 displayed a signal at 5.90-6.25 for NH protons which appeared as a broad singlet due to quadrupole effect¹⁸. However, this singlet disappeared when the sample was treated with deuterium oxide.* Compounds 4a-d and 8 did not show absorption for NH proton because of its absence in these compounds.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined on a Mel-Temp apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel H (B.D.H.) and ether-hexane (3:2) as eluent. Microanalyses were performed at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

1,1'-(1,3-Phenylene)bis(3-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (3) were prepared by the reaction of 1,3-diacetylbenzene (1) with an appropriate arylaldehyde (2) in presence of sodium hydroxide¹⁹. 3,3'-(1,4-Phenylene)bis(1-aryl-2-propen-1-ones) (7) were prepared by the reaction of 1,4-dicarboxaldehyde (5) with an appropriate methylaryl ketones (6) in presence of potassium hydroxide^{20,21}.

3,3'-m-Phenylenebis(5-aryl-2-pyrazolines) (4): A mixture of 3 (10 mmol), absolute alcohol (25 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was refluxed for

5–6 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from alcohol.

5,5'-(1,4-Phenylene)bis(1-acetyl-4,5-dihydro-3-aryl-1H-pyrazoles) (8): A mixture of 7 (10 mmol), absolute alcohol (25 ml), glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid.

Nitrosation of 4: A well-cooled solution of 4 (10 mmol) in 1:1 HCl (8 ml) was treated with a cold concentrated solution of sodium nitrite. The reaction mixture was then cooled in an ice-bath for 45–60 min and worked up to give 4a.

Acetylation of 4: A mixture of 4 (10 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) was refluxed for 4–5 h and then poured into cold water. The resulting solid (4b) was recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

Benzoylation/Benzene sulphonylation of 4: A solution of 4 (10 mmol) in pyridine (5 ml) was treated with benzoyl chloride/benzenesulphonyl chloride (20 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2–3 h and the contents then poured in ice-cold dilute HCl. The resulting solid (4c–d) was recrystallised from ethanol.

Antibacterial activity: Compounds 4, 4a–d and 8 were screened for their antibacterial activity by Vincent and Vincent method²² at a concentration of 100 µg ml⁻¹ using gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aureginosa* and *Escherichia coli* and also yeast *Proteus vulgaris* and *Candida albicans*. None of the compounds tested showed any antibacterial activity.

Antifungal activity: The antifungal activity of all the compounds was determined against three fungi *Curvularia lunata*, *Fusarium solani* and *Helminthosporium oryzae* following the procedure of Horsfall and Rich²³ with certain modifications. Almost all the compounds showed significant antifungal activity (Table 2). However, the antifungal activity was highest against *F. solani* in

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Substituents R	Antifungal activity (% Inhibition)		
		<i>C. l. nata</i>	<i>F. solani</i>	<i>H. oryzae</i>
4	H	98.60	100.00	70.25
	4-OH ₂	62.00	86.45	69.38
	4-(OH ₂) ₂ CH	85.20	93.86	82.50
	4-CH ₂ O	100.00	100.00	52.40
	4-C ₂ H ₅ O	100.00	100.00	74.60
	4-F	100.00	100.00	98.60
	4-Cl	100.00	100.00	100.00
	4-Br	96.46	100.00	88.60
	4-NO ₂	45.72	50.00	39.51
	2,4-(OH ₂ O) ₂	84.71	100.00	49.80
4a	H	78.40	85.20	33.40
	4-(OH ₂) ₂ OH	83.50	91.00	48.30
	4-Cl	100.00	100.00	78.46

(Table 2 contd.)

4b	H	100.00	100.00	73.20
	4-Cl	100.00	100.00	67.56
	4-NO ₂	78.00	84.20	59.34
4c	H	90.38	100.00	62.40
	4-OH ₂	80.00	76.00	45.00
	4-(OH ₂) ₂ OH	83.45	89.74	73.40
4d	H	100.00	100.00	49.50
	4-CH ₂	100.00	100.00	38.50
	4-C ₂ H ₅ O	100.00	100.00	68.50
8	H	100.00	100.00	60.24
	4-OH ₂	89.50	100.00	58.30
	4-CH ₂ O	100.00	100.00	56.40
	4-C ₂ H ₅ O	100.00	100.00	72.50
	4-Cl	100.00	100.00	79.32
	4-Br	93.40	100.00	68.50
	4-NH ₂	100.00	100.00	82.50
	2,4-(OH ₂ O) ₂	95.00	100.00	67.50

comparison to *C. lunata* while in *H. oryzae* showed lesser activity was shown. The antifungal activity increased with the halogen as a substituent in the phenyl moiety.

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References

- S. P. SACCHAR and A. K. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 142.
- D. B. REDDY, D. B. REDDY, N. S. REDDY and T. BALAJI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, **23**, 983.
- D. B. REDDY, T. SESHAMMA and B. V. REDDY, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1986, **122**, 19.
- D. B. REDDY, A. PADMAJA, T. SESHAMMA and M. V. R. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 400.
- A. A. OUF, M. M. EL-KERDAWY, A. M. FARGHALY and M. A. MOUSTAFA, *J. Drug. Res.*, 1979, **2**, 1.
- G. H. SAYED, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 364.
- G. H. SAYED and H. KJOESEN, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1980, **322**, 716.
- I. IRAGIMOV, R. A. GADZHILY, R. A. AGAEV, A. K. MURGUZOV, V. G. DZHAFAROV and V. I. BELYEVA, *Org. Khlororg. Sint.*, 1980, **28**.
- M. G. JOSHI and K. N. WADODKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 1090.
- J. ZAMOČKA, D. DVOVACKOVA, J. HEGER, A. NAGY and D. MHYNARCIK, *Czech. CS.*, 1982, **195**, 583.
- S. V. TSUKERMAN, V. M. NIKITCHENKO, V. P. MASLENNIKOVA and V. F. LAVRUSHIN, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin*, 1971, **7**, 1094.
- EL-RAYYES NIZAR, AL-JOHARY and A. A. JABBAR, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1985, **30**, 500.
- G. P. TOKMAKOVA, M. U. YU and N. S. PATALAKHA, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin*, 1980, **1**, 79.
- N. K. SANGWAN, B. S. VERMA and K. S. DHINDSA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 672.
- O. H. B. RAO, G. V. S. RAJU and P. V. N. RAJU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 400.
- V. G. THAKARE and K. N. WADODKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 610.
- K. S. NARSEH, B. S. VERMA and D. K. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 672.

18. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASSLER and T. C. MORRILL, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1981, p. 197.
19. M. HOSOGAWA, M. NOHARA, K. SAIGO, T. MORI and NAKASISHI, *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1984, 25, 561.
20. A. I. MAKHOTILO and V. G. TISCHENKO, *Zh. Org. Khim.*, 1973, 9, 1730.
21. S. V. TSUKERMAN, V. P. MASLEMIKOVA, V. M. NIKITCHENKO and V. F. LAVRUSHIN, *Zh. Russ. Ed.*, 1972, 38, 597.
22. J. C. VINCENT and H. W. VINCENT, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol Med.*, 1944, 55, 162
23. J. C. HORSFALL and S. RICH, *Indian Phytopathol.*, 1953, 6, 1.